

An Examination of Exploring the Factors Influencing the Job Satisfaction of Teachers towards Learner Performance

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Abstract:-

Introduction: The level of job satisfaction among teachers directly affects student achievement and instructional effectiveness. It is reasonable to argue that it is the foundation of any organization since it is an internal, positive feeling that fosters exceptional performance in any setting. There has been much discussion and disagreement over the link between performance and work satisfaction.

Purpose: This study is to investigate the relationship between job happiness and student performance. It is noteworthy because it identified the reasons behind subpar student performance, which helps the education ministry achieve its goal.

Methods: A qualitative design was employed because of its attentiveness, and the research approach was descriptive. The study used the purposive sampling method and data were collected using the semi-structured interview from 15 teachers and five (5) members of the management.

Results: The study found that the nature of the job; teachers' workload; recognition; motivation and support; the working environment; communication and teacher participation in decision-making and the stimulus of the leadership style encouraging teachers' job satisfaction.

Contribution: Study gives an insight to the role of teacher's job satisfaction on learner's performance in Africa.

Keywords:- Learning, Satisfaction, Performance, Influence and Decision-Making.

suggests that a variety of characteristics, including the work environment, job rewards, and overall attitude of teachers, are linked to their job happiness and how well their students perform.

According to Odembo (2013), job satisfaction refers to an employee's sentiments and attitudes regarding both internal and external factors related to their occupations and the company or organization. In the context of this study, it relates to the attitudes that educators have toward their jobs and the school where they work, as well as the management structure and any processes that may be in place.

Hage Geingob High School, located in the centre of Katutura, an informal community, faces difficulties in meeting national performance criteria (hagehighschool.com). The school has long been recognized for its excellent performance; examples include placing in the top three of the Junior Secondary Certificate (JSC) 2018 exams (www.nbc.na) and ranking in the top five of the Khomas region's best performing schools with the Namibia Senior Secondary Certificate Higher level (NSSCH) (New Era, 2019). It is against this background that this study sought to explore whether there is an influence on job satisfaction on learner performance to make improvements to maintain the academic performance at the school, so that it is consistent, and that excellence is striven for because performance measurement is a continuous process (Ivanov & Avasilcai, 2014). Academia is competitive and given that the school, according to its mission statement (hagehighschool.com) seeks to provide "learners with quality education and cultural program for them to be magnified citizens of our country equipped with the skills, value and attitudes so necessary to face the outside world", the progress is measured in the performance of the learners. Ivanov and Avasilcai (2014) affirm that the dynamic of the environment where organisations compete, such as schools, they develop a considerable interest for performance measurement. It is against this background that this study sought to explore the influence of teachers' job satisfaction on learner performance, using Hage Geingob as a case study.

I. INTRODUCTION

Most of a person's time is spent at work, which is an essential part of life (Ajuru, 2014). But contentment, or "the pleasure" that follows fulfilment, is what makes work meaningful (Ajuru, 2014, p. 12). While "work" refers to the teaching profession, "performance" refers to students' academic performance in the grade or the subject in general in the context of this study, which examines performance and job satisfaction as crucial variables in the educational setting. Academics (Odembo, 2013; Ajuru, 2014) agree that students' performance reflects their hard work and commitment. This

A. Statement of the problem

The exploration of the influence of teachers' job satisfaction allowed the researcher to determine the factors that cause job (dis)satisfaction and the influence of performance, which will enable the school and policy makers to establish or improve their performance systems.

The performance ranks of the Hage Geingob School have been mostly third or fifth and it has not been consistent like other schools in the Khomas region. As aforementioned, competition is necessary in an academic landscape that any school strives for excellence and quality deliverance to its learners is no exception to the competitive demands.

The fact that performance is an issue is evident in the fact that statistics in 2017 reveal that about 50 000 learners failed the national examination, 13 399 being Grade 12 learners and 27 000 Grade 10 learners (Smith, 2018). The high failure rate means the Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture did not reach its target of 40% tertiary institutions admission. And by exploring the influence of teacher's job satisfaction on learner performance, the study will be able to outline causes of poor learner performance, making it a significant study, enabling the school and respective ministry to meet goals and objectives. Performance has been a concern to most Namibian schools, and even schools that do not experience the issue of poor performance ought to be aware of the factors that cause poor performance, thereby developing strategies and systems to measure performance.

The study will provide solutions that will enable the ministry of education to reach its target in terms of academic performance. Given that most studies have not focused on the link between learner performance and satisfaction, this study is important, as it identifies the correlation by focusing mainly on the two variables. As such, it serves a significant source among the shelves of studies related to the subject, contributing to the literature for scholars who wish to pursue studies in such field.

B. Goals of the Research

The following are the goals of this study:

- Examine how Hage Geingob High School students' performance is affected by instructors' job satisfaction.
- Assess Hage Geingob High School's performance management systems; and
- Evaluate how these management system approaches affect the performance of the students.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. What we know about the area of inquiry?

➤ The concept of job satisfaction

According to Robbins (2018), job satisfaction is "the degree to which individuals feel positively and negatively about their jobs" (p. 37). It is a favorable attitude towards a vocation that arises from an examination of its qualities. Another word for job satisfaction is pleasure derived from one's perception of one's employment. The idea that employee performance is anchored by job happiness is no longer novel. Maximizing employee performance to achieve organizational goals is one of the most crucial objectives (Butler & Rose 2011). In order to do this, the organization needs highly motivated, content, and psychologically balanced workers in order to boost output and performance.

According to Robbins (2018), job satisfaction is a pleasant emotion that is more nuanced than it first appears (Robbins, 2018).

According to Robbins (2018), a person's overall attitude toward their work and the discrepancy between the benefits they receive and what they feel they should receive constitute the concept of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction has many components, and it can be difficult to define and has more implications for an organization than it first appears to (Robbins, 2018).

Job satisfaction is, therefore, more accurately determined when employees' desired expectations are met, where they experience a feeling of accomplishment, determining the degree of satisfaction. Expectations often vary from financial freedom and fringe benefits - depending on personal needs of the individual employee(s). These expectations vary, but there is a strategic way that human resource can measure the expectations, based on work-related factors such as timely remuneration, freedom to employees, creating room for promotion, including employees in decision-making and empathy towards employees (Oraman, Unakitan & Selen, 2011).

B. Which job satisfaction features were address on teachers' performance?

➤ Factors that influence job satisfaction

According to Arnold and Feldman (1996), various factors make employees to either feel positive or negative about their job. Moreover, some employees may be satisfied with a few aspects of their work but dissatisfied with others (Mullins, 2002). This statement means employees are usually not overall dissatisfied with their work but there are specific aspects they may be discontented about. The factors are, : recognition, the nature of work, the nature of work, supervision and management, and working conditions.

➤ *Performance management*

The process of establishing a work atmosphere or setting that encourages individuals to give their best work is known as performance management. It serves as the primary means by which managers inform staff members of expectations and provide feedback on how effectively they are accomplishing their work goals (CIPD, 2009). Several components of the profession of people management are combined with it, especially learning and development. As a result, performance management is a crucial component of the leadership job and will strengthen the bonds with team members by creating a common understanding of what needs to be accomplished and provide a method for motivating and leading others to achieve it.

A PMS is a methodical approach to converting organizational intent into unit/team goals and individual performance; enhancing performance on both the individual and team levels to meet organizational goals by guaranteeing a common understanding of goals, outcomes, values, and priorities; and offering pertinent coaching and development along with targeted and pertinent feedback (Shackleton, 2007). Therefore, the PMS is a collaborative process including managers and supervisors, teams and units, and individuals; it is centered strategic competency development and management by contract rather than by demand.

The PMS serves as a framework for strategic planning and management. It also helps to create, clarify, and improve understanding of organizational goals, priorities, and values. Lastly, it unites the organization by integrating individual performance with organizational goals. In 2015, Armstrong.

An organization uses performance measurement to keep an eye on key components of its systems, programs, and care procedures. Information is gathered to show how well these components are operating, and this data is then utilized to support decisions made by the organization over time (HRSA, 2011). Performance is usually assessed and contrasted with the aims and objectives of the organization. Performance measure results give information on how well a collective's current programs are operating and how best to use its resources to maximize the efficiency and effectiveness of the programs (HRSA, 2011).

According to Armstrong (2015), there are two viewpoints that should be considered when assessing a performance management system: the management's assessment and the employee's assessment. These two demands should be satisfied through performance management. The following inquiries served as a foundation for the examination of the elements impacting instructors' job satisfaction regarding student performance:

C. *What are the current theories?*

The Motivation-Hygiene Theory, the Job Characteristics Model, the Dispositional Approach, and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs are the four basic theories that contribute to our understanding of job satisfaction. Maslow's hierarchy of needs was used in this study to evaluate how well teachers' needs are being addressed. Because the essential requirements are linked to the employees' emotions, the analysis will ascertain the degree of job satisfaction (Huitt, 2017). It has been suggested that Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory is among the simplest approaches to analysing human behaviour; but, in the digital age, a deeper level of complexity is required to comprehend people' place in modern societies (Jonathan, 2016).

Maslow's hierarchy is frequently depicted as a pyramid, with the "esteem needs," which he believes to be less vital, at the top and the "deficit needs," which are most vital to survival, at the base. According to this theory, people progress through a basic set of hierarchical motives in a particular order depending on their psychological and physiological demands. Maslow listed these "needs" in the following order of significance: safety; love and belonging; esteem; self-actualization; biological or physiological needs.

Despite being a psychological theory, the hierarchy of needs has been applied extensively in the field of education. One of education's main goals is to help people learn and make the process meaningful for them so that it affects and benefits their lives. This seems to be where the relevance to education comes from. According to the hierarchy of needs, a person must be motivated to reach their predetermined goals for learning to occur and information to be retained (Jonathan, 2016). The hierarchy of needs can be viewed from the perspective of learning and teaching, however learning and teaching are impacted if the basic physiological requirements of humans are not met. As a result, education and personal growth will drop in importance (Mittleman, 1991).

D. *What need further testing because evidence is lacking, inconclusive, contradictory, limited?*

Whilst the above research indicates a strong correlation between job satisfaction and teachers' performance having a strong link, there has not been a substantial testing to examine how job satisfaction is in terms of effective performance and how it allows for this to occur. With educational pedagogy now changing rapidly due to the introduction of more personal technologies and a search for better outcomes by school management, the need for evidence-based research is essential.

E. *What designs methods are faulty?*

The conceptual framework of the investigation, analytical techniques, and decision-making procedures utilized to tackle the main research issue of your study are all established by the research design. By taking the time to create a comprehensive research design, you may better arrange your

ideas, define the parameters of your investigation, increase the validity of your results, and steer clear of drawing erroneous or insufficient conclusions. Consequently, the quality and dependability of your findings as well as the total significance of your study will be lowered if any component of your research design is faulty or inadequately developed (Labaree, 2023). Following are a few typical issues that are seen when creating a research project, in no particular order:

➤ *Inadequate Methodological Approach:*

A clear, comprehensive plan outlining the generation, collection, and analysis of data must be included in the design. Make sure the information gathering strategy is in line with the research questions that need to be answered and the topic of the study.

➤ *Vicinity Sampling*

This refers to employing a sample which is based not upon the aims of your study, but rather, is based upon the vicinity of a certain group of people. The units of analysis, whether they be persons, places, events, or things, must not be predicated merely on ease of access and convenience.

➤ *Methods or Tools*

Clearly state the methods (like semi-structured interviews) or tools (like questionnaires) that were employed to collect the data. Your research design should specify how the method or tool will yield data that is dependable to address the research problem's related concerns (Labaree, 2023).

➤ *Statistical Treatment*

In quantitative research, you must provide a detailed explanation of how you plan to arrange the unprocessed data to do analysis. Typically, this entails summarizing the data using central tendency measures, such as mean, median, and mode, which aid in the researcher's explanation of the data's concentration and enable the researcher to derive significant conclusions about significant trends or patterns within the data.

➤ *Vocabulary*

Research frequently uses technical terms and jargon that the reader is probably already familiar with. But refrain from using jargon that is too technical or pseudo-technical. Vocabulary issues can also include the inappropriate use of clichés, colloquialisms, and terminology distinctive to a certain culture in academic writing. Further details on appropriate word usage.

➤ *Ethical Dilemmas*

In the methods section of qualitative research studies, you must describe how you plan to reduce participant risk (also known as "respondents" or "human subjects") during the data collection phases while maintaining sufficient ability to address the research problem. If you don't, the reader may begin to doubt the impartiality and veracity of the entire study (Labaree, 2023).

➤ *Limitations of Study*

Every study has its limits. Your research strategy should explicitly indicate the amount of missing data and predict and explain the reasons for these constraints. It is imperative to provide an explanation of the potential effects these restrictions may have on the validity of your findings, as well as how you mitigated their significance.

F. *What contribution will my work make?*

Research can be a valuable tool in helping educators recognize and comprehend practice issues, promote reform, and show how their efforts have an influence on the classroom. The Namibian education system, particularly the school system, is characterised by the lack of resources, poor infrastructure, and lack of educated/trained staff, as well as learners enduring various socio-economic challenges at home (Amutenya, 2016). There have also been reports about learner dropouts, teenage pregnancies, and complaints about poor infrastructure in the daily newspapers. For instance, Ngutjinazo (2019) reported that the respective ministry struggles to meet all the infrastructural needs of schools in Namibia. And these needs are usually attributed to the fact that most schools in Namibia were built during the pre-independent era – and as such, the structures need to be upgraded. The respective minister at the time, Katrina Hanse-Himarwa, elaborated that there is a need to renovate and upgrade existing, ageing infrastructure (Ngutjinazo, 2019).

In his investigation into the causes of low teacher morale in the Oshana region, Shavuka (2019) discovered that low morale is linked to student academic performance in secondary schools in the Oshana educational region and is related to the work environment, learner motivation, parental involvement in their children's education, and the school's leadership style.

➤ *Theoretical framework*

The Theory of Job Satisfaction: Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Maslow's hierarchy of requirements is modeled like a pyramid, which illustrates how meeting a person's base needs enables them to climb the pyramid. Physiological necessities are at the base of the pyramid. As one moves up the pyramid, one has needs for safety, esteem, and a sense of love and belonging. Self-actualization is the final need category at the top of the pyramid (Falcon, 2022).

By offering amenities like a small kitchen or vending machine, together with financial and non-financial perks like health insurance and compensation, a company can assist in meeting the physiological demands of its workforce. When workers' physiological needs are met, they look to their jobs to meet their needs for safety. It can be given by making people feel secure at work. Establishing a safe and upbeat work atmosphere will assist companies in accomplishing this.

The Falcon (2022) The next level in the hierarchy of needs is a sense of love and belonging, which can be fostered in

employees through their manager and coworkers' admiration. An employee has to feel like their career is progressing and that their activities are making a difference in the company's performance in order to feel valued. For employees to reach the objective of self-actualization, they must believe that their efforts have been fully utilized. It ultimately leads to job satisfaction by empowering and motivating them.

➤ *Motivation - Hygiene Theory in Job Satisfaction Theory*

Herzberg's motivation-cleanliness theory states that the two primary components that influence employee satisfaction are motivation and hygiene. Hygiene lowers discontent, but motivation increases satisfaction. Enhancing job happiness are motivators or satisfiers. Individuals are motivated by several factors such as job position, responsibility, personal growth, opportunity for progress, performance and achievement, and acknowledgment. It is necessary to enhance workplace incentive aspects (Labaree, 2023).

Dissatisfying factors may include low pay, unfavorable working circumstances, a cramped workspace, toxic or dysfunctional relationships with coworkers and the boss, and inadequate supervision in an environment where rules and politics are strong. Employee dissatisfaction will arise from unimproved conditions.

➤ *Job Satisfaction Theory: Job Characteristics Model*

The Job Characteristics Model was developed in 1976 by Hackman and Oldham to assist employers in providing their workers with a more engaging and interesting work environment. The model states that five characteristics can be modified to increase the level of engagement, motivation, and satisfaction at work: skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback (Falcon, 2022).

Through job importance, task identity, and skill variety, workers can have meaningful work experiences. The Falcon (2022) Employees who have autonomy at work feel accountable for the results of their labour. Employee feedback on their work aids in their understanding of its impact. If they need to adjust, it will support them. High levels of internal motivation, excellent work output, high levels of work and job happiness, and low absenteeism and turnover are all results of these psychological states.

➤ *Employment Contentment Theory: A Dispositional Perspective*

Trial theory, also known as dispositional theory, was created by Staw, Bell, and Clausen. It was centered on the temperament of the worker (Falcon, 2022). They made the argument that a person's personality has an impact on their level of job satisfaction. The reason for this is because an employee's definition of a positive experience may differ from another's (Falcon, 2022).

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research design

Kothari (2004) advises researchers to have a research approach and design, because it serves as a guide for the entire study. It is for this reason the researcher ensured there is a research design to steer the process of the research. Patton (2015) confirms that a research design is a plan of action on how to go about an empirical research study, where conditions are arranged for collection and analysis of data to combine relevance to the purpose of the study with the research budget. In procedure. The conceptual structure within which this study was conducted is a case study; the study explored the variables (job satisfaction and performance) using a specific case – Hage Geingob Secondary School. Creswell (2013) asserts that case studies are typically designs of qualitative research, and it is effective in obtaining in-depth data on a subject under study. The method was suitable, as it was affordable and it accommodated the research instruments that were effective for the data collection.

B. Population

A population of a study refers to the entire group of interest with common characteristics to the variables of the study. The population of this study, therefore, consisted of all teachers, learners and management at Hage Geingob High School. The school has about 30 teachers, 10 members of management and 1 000 learners. Hence, the total population was 1 040 individuals that served as interest of the study.

C. Sample

Sampling refers to the selection, without bias and with as much precision as resources allow, the items of elements from which or whom researchers intend to collect data (McGiven, 2003), derived from the population of the study. Using the non-probability sampling technique, the researcher was able to purposively select 15 teachers and five (5) members of management to participate in the study. Moreover, 60 learners were observed during class to determine aspects of relationships between their teachers.

The population members who are most likely to be informed and aware about the phenomena of interest were chosen through the technique of purposive sampling (Badugela, 2012). According to Polkinghorne (2005), purposive sampling is more concerned with gathering information that can help clarify and improve knowledge of the experience than it is with drawing conclusions from statistics. Purposive sampling was employed based on the characteristics of the population and the objectives of the study, which are subjective, selective, and judgemental; thus, there was no guarantee that the entire population of the study would be represented in the sample (Leedy & Ormrod, 2013).

D. Research instruments

Data were collected using the observation guide for learners, as well as separate interview guides for teachers and management. The interviews were semi-structured, allowing for open-ended questions and probing. Creswell (2013) states that semi-structured interviews are effective for qualitative research because it allows researchers to dig deeply into the subject they are studying.

The interview questions were prepared beforehand to guide the conversation and keep respondents focused on the topic; it is easy to end up going off topic. Moreover, Patton (2015) suggests that semi-structured interviews allow respondents to open up about sensitive issues, enabling the collection of qualitative data (Cresswell, 2013) because qualitative data is concerned with the subjective assessment of attitudes, opinions and behaviour.

The semi-structured interview sessions were recorded with the researcher's cell phone and they were saved according to the labels given to the participants, for example Participant 1, etc. The researcher ensured that the data were classified accordingly so they were transferred from the cell phone to the laptop in folders that were categorised as: teachers and management. This data was kept safely, locked with security password to avoid access from anyone else other than the researcher.

E. Data analysis

The study's goals, the research tools, and the levels of Maslow's hierarchy of needs were all taken into consideration when thematic analysis was employed to examine the qualitative data. It was noteworthy that the researcher allowed opportunity for themes that surfaced from the data gathering, analysis, and literature evaluation. To aid in the analysis, the recordings were transcribed and made available in written form.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

A. The impact of teachers' job satisfaction on learner performance

Job satisfaction affects learner's performance and educational improvement is not possible without first improving these two factors. Robbins (2018) found that factors that contribute to job satisfaction have an impact on job satisfaction because it energises teachers to work towards the attainment of the school, which is the ultimate goal of any school. Teaching provides teachers with opportunities to advance professional in so many ways. Additionally, teaching provides opportunities for career advancement especially when to choose methods of delivery and source for the new teaching skills. The participants stated that:

"The benefit of being a teacher is that you will always have time to study if you are upgrading your qualifications" (P2).

"As a teacher you always learn a new concept every day from your colleagues and learners" (P4).

The study found that when there are changes in the curriculum it enhances teaching skills as teachers are given sufficient training. Moreover, the school is also guided by policies, and teachers are given opportunities to apply for study leave so that they may go and further their studies. In the current educational landscape, parents, the community, and all other stakeholders have placed a great deal of responsibility on school administrators to ensure that students achieve the educational goals that have been set forth (Bambrick-Santoya & Peiser, 2012). Bambrick-Santoya and Peiser (2012) further state that an employee's job should be uplifting and offers development. The teacher's job satisfaction has a great impact on the learner's performance especially when the nature of their job allows them interact with the learners and advance professionally. The nature of the job of the teaching provides them with life time career goal, and some teachers become lectures or tutors.

"I am motivated by my job to do an excellent job because I learn a lot from my colleagues and learners" (P10).

"As a teacher I have gained a lot of experience and skills which motivates me to educate my learners" (P8).

Teaching provides teachers with opportunities to use variety of skills. Teachers are managers who manages a classroom and discipline. Hence, teachers acquire different types of skills from working with different personality and background which gain them interpersonal skills, intrapersonal skills, communication skills and time management skills. Teachers are involved in sports and many others extra curriculum activities which at the end equip them with various skills such as sports skills. Additional to this, teachers provide learners with opportunity to use variety of studying skills and methods to excel academic.

Robbins (2018) defines job satisfaction as a favorable attitude toward a vocation that arises from an assessment of its attributes. Because the school has tools like copy machines and electronic whiteboards that allow teachers to transition from conventional teaching methods to more modern ones employing new instructional media, teacher job satisfaction affects student achievement. With internet connectivity and a connection to other schools, teachers can access a wealth of resources including updated curricula. There are memorandums and previous exam questions available. This result suggests that instructors' job satisfaction increased when they kept up with the latest technologies and trends. As a result, these educators are open to implementing these novel ideas and trends in the field of education.

B. Teacher's workload

The evidence indicates that instructors' workloads have an impact on their ability to produce high-quality work. Overall job satisfaction was negatively impacted by workload and stress levels. The attendees regretted that:

"Sometimes the heavy workload affects our performance because we are exhausted and don't deliver great work" (P15).

"If the workload is light, one can navigate through his/her work with ease" (P. 3).

This suggests that teachers' stress and discontent are exacerbated by their workload. Teachers' workloads must therefore match their designated working hours and availability; if they are assigned additional tasks, upper management must provide assistance for them. According to Robbins (2018), workers are more likely to experience job satisfaction if they find their work engaging and are not overworked.

C. Recognition, motivation, and teachers support.

The effectiveness of the school in helping or supporting teachers with student discipline, curriculum, instructional strategies, and environment adjustment is known as teacher support. Teacher's support from colleagues and the management plays a significant role in motivating and recognising the teacher's work in improving learner's performance. The type of recognition teachers receive from their immediate supervisors includes appraisal, positive praises during staff meeting for the job well done, awards ceremonies are made to award teachers for the best results in the academic year. The participants claimed that:

"When the management recognise your hard work in improving learner's performance, it makes you work hard and satisfied in your work" (P1).

"I am grateful that my colleagues are helpful and have an open-door policy to assist those who are struggling to do their jobs effectively" (P12).

According to the report, the school has an open-door policy, meaning that any teacher in need of help can get it. Administrative assistance has a favourable effect on teachers' job satisfaction, according to Dugguh and Dennis (2014). Hage Geingob Secondary School has adequate space for support, according to the current analysis. The participants believe that school administrators have a duty to ensure that teachers are happy in their jobs.

Teacher assistance is the term used to describe how administrators and Heads of Departments assist teachers in completing their jobs and enhancing their instruction. Opportunities for schoolteachers' professional development are greatly aided by their superiors' help. The study found out that some supervisors do not often give support and assistance to the teachers. However, teachers seek for help

through their supervisors when the need arise. New teachers are inducted and guided in topics which they are not comfortable teaching. Yet, most of the times teachers are on their own, unless looking for information themselves elsewhere, most of the time teachers are not given support and they are on their own. Teachers at school have different activities that they are in charge of and they are awarded according to the effort they have put on those activities. Moreover, learners are provided with feedback on their academic progress every term, therefore learners receive recognitions and motivation from the school in the form of praises and academic awards given twice in a year.

D. The working environment

Teacher's motivation towards job satisfaction is the working environment. The study findings revealed that the school under study has positive environment with the spirit of working hard since Hage Geingob High Secondary School is a school of excellence, teachers are fantasised by this slogan to work hard which at the end they will feel fulfilled. The school environment enhances teaching and learning for academic excellence to some and to some teachers the school environment is not conducive.

"The schools working environment is conducive and this motivates one to do their job at ease and this is reflected in the performance of the learners" (P11).

"Everybody gets along well with each other at the school" (P18).

"The school handles its discipline cases very well and the classroom are conducive for learners to learn and for the teacher to teach" (P15).

One's productivity is greatly influenced by their workplace. A pleasant classroom atmosphere helps teachers and students feel at ease and comfortable when they are teaching and studying, claim Munyengabe et al. (2016). Hage Geingob has well-organized classrooms with readily available materials like textbooks, a whiteboard, and a syllabus, despite the school's outdated technology. The study's conclusions showed that to create a conducive learning environment, disruptive behaviours are managed both within and outside of the classroom. The institution is best known for its strong academic standards and excellent discipline. At the secondary or primary school levels, a well-designed classroom is beneficial because it inspires teachers to be enthusiastic and engaged in their daily teaching tasks. These findings are consistent with Suson (2019) who narrated that the product of teaching-learning process is determined not just by the performance of teachers, but also the quality of the environment where they are working.

E. Communication and teacher participation in decision making.

Teachers' morale is raised and they are motivated to perform more correctly and productively when there is communication and they are involved in decision making. This boosts efficiency and productivity while improving job satisfaction. The majority of participants in the study, however, believed that there was a lack of communication at the school when it came to making important decisions.

“Some teachers are excluded from the decision-making process at the school” (P20).

“When we air our opinions, they are regarded as irrelevant and we are considered to be trouble brewer and this affects our satisfaction with the management” (P17).

“Our opinions are valued at all hence sometimes you just keep quiet” (P14).

The study uncovered that there are groups within the school, and that teachers label each other if you question the management decision. Some participants feel that the communication which is utilised at the school is more on autocratic, dictating information to the staff. Although minority feels there is proper communication, whereby they are free to speak their minds but their opinions and contributions are not valued or taken seriously. Furthermore, some decision is made hierarchy and no much involvement of the teachers. Oraman, Unakitan and Selen (2011) state that including employees in decision making of the organisation gives them a purpose and makes them feel like they belong. Teachers are just informed on what to do but they do not contribute in decision-making. Lastly, the study uncovered that the management makes all of the decisions on behalf of the teachers and not all decisions involve teachers, not all suggestions are taken.

F. Leadership style/influence and teamwork

A positive rapport between teachers and other subordinates as well as the heads of the schools is linked to teacher satisfaction. The findings indicate that a teacher's level of job satisfaction is significantly influenced by the leadership of the school. The results of the study support the claim made by Bambrick-Santoyo and Peiser (2012) that school leadership plays a substantial role in influencing student performance since it has a direct impact on the learning environment within the school. The results of the survey showed that teachers place a high importance on respect between themselves and the administration of the school as a factor that influences the development of a positive working relationship. The attendees made note of the following:

“It is a good thing for mutual respect to exist between the teacher and the management so that the teacher can be satisfied with his/her job and produce satisfactory results” (P10).

“Respect is a mutual concept and if it evident in the teacher and management relationship then good fruits will be produced” (P13).

“The reason why things work effectively at this school is because of the good working relationship between the principal and the teachers” (P14).

From above data, it is seen that if the good relationship is maintained at the workplace the level of job satisfaction will be increased. This implied that good relationship between the management and teachers will likely attain the goal and objectives of the school. Therefore, teachers are happy and interested to work in the place where there is a good relationship with their school management. The study found out that the school management and teacher's mutual respect has a strong influence on learner's learning and performance.

The evidence stated above suggests that maintaining positive working connections will increase job satisfaction. This implied that if administrators and teachers got along well, the school's goals and objectives would probably be met. Teachers are therefore happy and willing to work at schools where there is a positive working relationship between the management and instructors. The study found that respect between instructors and the school administration has a major impact on students' learning and performance.

The study concludes by making the case that teachers' job satisfaction and productivity are significantly impacted by the nature of their interaction with school administration. The principle is the primary figurehead who oversees not only the day-to-day operations of the school but also the professional development of the instructors. As a result, the leadership that the head of the school gives to the faculty and students determines the performance of any given institution (Vidoni & the European Commission, 2011). Studies show that a successful school principle is the institution's leader and has a significant impact on teachers' intentions to continue as educators because of the way he shapes their attitudes toward teaching.

G. Performance management systems at Hage Geingob High School

Human development and the upkeep of socially responsive political and economic systems are two reasons why a well-functioning educational system is crucial (Modisaotsile, 2012). Good things happen when a performance management system is designed properly. Feedback between leaders and teachers is either less frequent or non-existent in the absence of a system. Systems that specify goals and work schedules are necessary for schools. More significantly, educators need to know how they can do better and want feedback on how they are doing. The study asked the participants about the performance management system at their school, and they stated that:

"I am not aware of the performance management at the Hage Geingob" (P19).

"There is a performance management system at Hage Geingob SS but I have no understanding of how it works" (P11).

"The performance management at the school is dormant, nobody takes it serious" (P16).

The study found out that majority of the participants are not aware of the performance management, and the participants that knows it don't fully understand it. The study findings differ from Eslami and Gharakhani (2012) observation that employees are aware of the performance management policy that measures their progress hence they become satisfied with their work. The study defines the performance management systems as a strategic and integrated approach of conveying continued success to institutions by developing the people in a way that improves group and personal performance. Some of the participants define it as how you manage to supervise the performance of the institution by measuring the output against the input.

H. The benefits of Performance Management System

Since they shape the next generation of leaders, educators are regarded as the foundation of the nation. Nonetheless, some educational institutions neglect to acknowledge the value of teachers' professional development in enhancing the school's productivity. In order to maximize output and boost employee morale, a strong performance management system must be developed. It's a thorough process that requires each participant to fully cooperate and participate. The following advantages of performance management systems were emphasized by the participants:

"It improves one's motivation and focus" (P12).

"It empowers the workforce" (P9)

"It fortifies the basis of an individual's aptitude." (15 P)

"It allows proper evaluation and raises retention and morale" (P2)

Armstrong (2015) pointed out that while assessing a performance management system, there are two viewpoints to consider: management's assessment of the system's effectiveness and employee evaluation of the system. The benefits of the performance management at the school are that the management can identify problems that hinders academic performance then it will assist the school in performing better. The study results show that performance management systems enable the school to make some reformations that will enhance learning and teaching at the school. The school's deployment of a performance management system aids in the revision and establishment of specific goals that will raise the institution's academic performance. The performance management system

enables the school to come up with strategies such as extra classes and holiday classes to compliment on the normal teaching hours which are not sufficient. Through the performance management systems, the school management assess the performance of the teachers in their respective subject and once a high failure percentage is detected, the management devices ways to handle the situation and addresses effectively it, to improve the future results of the school.

V. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The performance of learners is impacted by job happiness, and increasing these two aspects is necessary for educational advancement. The goal of any school is learner happiness, high-quality instruction, and school progress. Teaching provides teachers with opportunities to advance professional in so many ways. Additionally, teaching provides opportunities for career advancement especially when to choose methods of delivery and source for the new teaching skills.

According to the study, curricular modifications improve teaching abilities since they provide teachers with adequate training. Teachers could apply for study leave so they can continue their education, and the school is also governed by laws. The degree to which a teacher is happy in their position affects how well their students perform, particularly if their work includes opportunities for professional growth and interaction with students. Due to the nature of their work, instructors can pursue careers as lecturers or tutors for the rest of their lives.

Majority of the participants are of the view that teaching add to their knowledge and skill because they both learn from teachers and learners. When a teacher delivers a lesson and achieve the objectives of the lesson, they feel fulfilled especially when the learners understand and have mastered the concepts. Teachers are also inspired to see their learners passing. The nature of the teaching job is fulfilling because the school provide an environment for personal growth because teachers at the school are given different responsibilities and they are expected to carry out these responsibilities independently. Thus, in the process, they are able to learn, plan and organise their tasks and with all these kind of qualities it will enable them to grow professional.

Robbins (2018) defines job satisfaction as a favorable attitude toward a vocation that arises from an assessment of its attributes. Because the school has tools like copy machines and electronic whiteboards that allow teachers to transition from conventional teaching methods to more modern ones employing new instructional media, teacher job satisfaction affects student achievement. With internet connectivity and a connection to other schools, teachers can access a wealth of resources including updated curricula. There are

memorandums and previous exam questions available. This result suggests that instructors' job satisfaction increased when they kept up with the latest technologies and trends. As a result, these educators are open to implementing these novel ideas and trends in the field of education.

➤ Conclusion

This study set out to identify the reasons behind subpar learner performance as well as investigate the impact of work happiness on learner performance. We may conclude that several things affect how satisfied teachers are with their jobs and how well their students perform. But when these things are well managed, the teachers get good at what they do and are happy with their work. Teachers specifically mentioned how their workload affects their satisfaction, saying that a heavy workload makes them unhappy and exhausted, but a light and manageable workload allows them to carry out their duties with ease, which improves student performance. The study's findings demonstrated that Hage Geingob High School's performance management system needs immediate attention in order for the institution to gauge its teachers' effectiveness. The study concluded that the reason the performance management system is helpful in raising student performance is that it gives teachers more motivation and focus to meet the requirements of their students and provide high-quality instruction.

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